

REFLECTING ARBITRABILITY ISSUES OF INTERNATIONAL COMMERCIAL LAW IN DOMESTIC LEGISLATION OF UZBEKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

The arbitrability of disputes is examined in this article from a legal theoretical perspective. In addition, it evaluates the extent to which arbitration is governed by foreign law and considers the implications of applying this knowledge to Uzbek law. The national legislation on the subject of arbitrability contains abstractions, so it is important to make sure that these provisions are accurately reflected in the law to prevent future disagreements over an arbitrator's competence or discrepancies between the national legislation and international practice.

Keywords: arbitrability, domestic law, *ratione materiae*, *ratione personae*, jurisdiction, regulatory space, fork-in-the-road, arbitration, mediation.

Introduction. Arbitrability determines whether a disagreement is "arbitrable," that is, if it may be resolved by arbitration.¹ Despite the fact that arbitration is a private procedure, the recognition and execution of a specific judgment may have an influence on any States involved. Certain situations may include "public" rights and concerns, or third-party interests, and in such cases, the settlement of conflicts through a private court may be contested. If the disagreement cannot be arbitrated, the arbitral tribunal's jurisdiction is restricted, and the claim must instead be filed in domestic courts.²

There may be restrictions on a party's ability to enter into arbitration agreements, which means that certain entities (e.g., States or State entities) may not be allowed to enter into arbitration agreements or may require special authorization to do so due to policy considerations ("subjective arbitrability"), or limitations based on the subject matter ("objective arbitrability"). Certain conflicts may entail such important public policy problems that domestic law reserves solely to the jurisdiction of domestic courts.

Arbitrability is not easily determined in the abstract. One must first determine the law governing arbitrability. Whether a dispute is arbitrable may change depending on which law governs.³ Furthermore, decision of arbitrability may occur at various phases of the arbitral procedure and in various fora. These

include (a) proceedings before the tribunal at the outset of the proceedings; (b) proceedings before state courts, either as a preliminary matter to be resolved before the arbitration can proceed or as a question of whether the award should be set aside; and (c) proceedings before the court of enforcement. As a result there are many options regarding which law may apply to determining questions of arbitrability. Gary Born⁴ lists these as:

[...(a) the law of the nation in which enforcement of an award is being or will eventually be sought; (b) the law governing the parties' arbitration agreement; (c) the law of the seat of the arbitration; (d) the law of the judicial forum where an arbitration agreement is sought to be enforced; (e) the law that provides the basis for the relevant substantive claim that is said to be non-arbitrable; or (f) a uniform international definition of non-arbitrability derived from the New York Convention (or other relevant conventions)...]

Scholars can easily tell the difference between subjective and objective

arbitrability. Subjective arbitrability (or "arbitrability *ratione personae*") refers to the inability of certain persons or entities, such as states or municipal governments, to submit their disputes to arbitration owing to their status or role⁵. The objective arbitrability (or "*arbitrability ratione materiae*") focuses on whether a certain subject-matter can be settled through arbitration. According to Prof. Böckstiegel, in determining whether a matter is arbitrable one should consider that both criteria –

i.e. subjective and objective arbitrability – supplement each other.⁶

As a result, the fact that a dispute concerns taxation is not a bar to arbitration. Arbitrability, on the other hand, is concerned with what the arbitral tribunal has been requested to undertake in relation to the subject-matter of taxes. In accordance with the trend away from subject-matter arbitrability and toward general arbitrability, if the tribunal is requested to resolve a contractual dispute that does not entail a decision of the legitimacy of a State's sovereign activities, this should be arbitrable. However, if the tribunal is requested to resolve a substantive tax issue involving the sovereign interests of the State involved, this should not be arbitrable.

Materials and methods. The article examines international business dispute arbitration as well as international law's control of relationships including international private law. In this respect, the legal foundation for the regulation of the subject of arbitration in other countries is analyzed, and it is suggested to offer a solution to the problems that now exist in Uzbek law.

Results. The determination of the law controlling arbitrability is critical. Despite the overall trend toward broadening the scope of arbitrable conflicts, national laws frequently diverge. A variety of conflicts that are not arbitrable under one country's legislation are arbitrable in another when the interests concerned are seen to be less important. Bribery approaches are one illustration of existing discrepancies. Bribery is a vitiating element in all contracts in many nations, although it can be evaluated by arbitrators. In some nations, not only is bribery illegal, but charges of bribery cannot be examined by arbitrators, preventing it from being legitimised by a business or consulting contract. As a result of the frequency of excessive commissions considered bribes, consultant contracts pertaining to public procurement are not arbitrable in various nations. The legislation regulating the arbitrability of a dispute may differ depending on where and when the question arises in the proceedings. Tribunals may use different criteria in deciding this statute than courts, and the criteria used by courts at the post-award stage may differ from those used at the pre-award stage. International documents, such as the Geneva Protocol and the New York Convention, may include references to arbitrability and public policy limits, as well as provide for specific repercussions when applied to an arbitration agreement or a judgment. When we try to define important sectors with such limits, before we get to national law, an obvious issue is whether there are provisions in international treaties or other documents stating that specific areas are not arbitrable. Because neither the Geneva Protocol, the Geneva Conventions, nor the New York Agreement contain such provisions, proposals have been made to change the latter by including a list of non-arbitral subject topics for each member state, or by including such a list as an appendix or a new convention. However, these suggestions were never implemented, and rightly so, because it appears unrealistic to achieve a well- defined workable list to deal with the wide variety of different situations that occur and are acceptable to all or most member states despite the differences found in different national systems. As a result, we only find any advice in international treaties in a few unusual circumstances.

Discussions. After all, an arbitration agreement drafted and signed in compliance with all requirements, on the one hand, will be reduced to nothing if it allows for the transfer of a dispute that does not come within the jurisdiction of arbitration. On the other hand, while evaluating issues on recognition and execution of arbitral decisions under Article 31 of the Economic Procedural Code (hereafter referred to as the EPC), state courts are likewise interested in the topic of

conflicts that may (or may not) be examined by arbitration. Disputes arising from all commercial relations, including contractual and non-contractual obligations, are recognized as arbitrable in Uzbekistan, according to general rules and as a result of Part 2 of Article 4 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On International Commercial Arbitration" (hereinafter referred to as the Law). As can be seen from the preceding rule, a wide range of legal connections aiming at extracting profit are provided, originating between civil turnover subjects: persons, legal entities, and the state.

Article 1 of the UNCITRAL Model Law on International Commercial Arbitration (hereafter referred to as the Model Law) provides a general knowledge of the subject. By all circumstances, it is worth acknowledging that the spectrum of such ties is extremely large, and that ignoring them is difficult, notwithstanding the Model Law's endeavor. Without duplicating the content of the footnote to Article 1 of the Model Law, the author believes it is necessary to stand in solidarity with this list of issues that can be brought to arbitration. All of these or comparable conflicts may be reviewed and resolved in arbitration under Uzbekistan's legislation. Other connected conflicts include:

- trading of crypto assets on the crypto exchange;
- the deployment of futures trading on commodities exchanges and the establishment of an electronic logistics trading platform for product shipment by road.

Corporate squabbles. Corporate conflicts are one of the types of disputes. Article 25 of the EPC assigns corporate conflicts to the jurisdiction of economic courts, and Article 30 of this Code gives a non-exhaustive list of instances in this category. These forms of business conflicts appear to have evolved through many years of court practice and are common in Uzbekistan's legal reality. These are disputes concerning the formation, reorganization, and liquidation of legal entities, disputes concerning shares, portions, dividends, and disputes of participants concerning the invalidity of transactions made by legal entities, and disputes

concerning the issue of securities, and disputes concerning the convening of general meetings, and disputes concerning appealing.

Disputes involving a single person. There is no limitation against considering and resolving individual claims in international business arbitration. The term "parties" is used in Uzbekistan's arbitration statute. Individuals, legal entities, and the State can all be parties to a dispute resulting from contractual or non-contractual duties. As a result, disagreements involving a single person are

arbitrable. But there's another question here. Even in the absence of higher instances, the consideration and settlement of a case in international business arbitration is considerably more expensive than in state courts. Not everyone is prepared to pay the costs of arbitration (fees, expenditures, attorneys' fees, travel expenses, and so on). In this regard, in the concept of arbitration procedures, this problem is frequently seen as an individual's misunderstanding or delusion during the conclusion and signing of an arbitration agreement. That is, this individual was unaware of the significance of the contract's arbitration clause. Such an interpretation may potentially result in the arbitration agreement being declared invalid, because the party, an individual, signed the arbitration agreement in mistake.

To conclude, it is important to note that determining scope of the arbitrability is essential to avoid future conflict of laws. There is no doubt about arbitrability in disputes concerning only the individual interests of the parties. However, if the dispute shows elements of public interest, it does not automatically imply that it is not arbitrable.⁷ In addition, amending arbitrability related provisions in related laws, especially, in Law on International Commercial Arbitration and Economic Procedural Code, and specifying the disputes, which could be arbitrable clearly helps resolving disputes without additional need of interpretation of laws.

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